

Antibacterial screening of *Calatropis procera* and *Tribulus terresteris* against *Xanthomonas* sp., *E. coli* and *Salmonella* sp.

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Abstract

Calatropis procera and *Tribulus terresteris* plants were screened as comparative study of plant extracts against *Xanthomonas* sp., *Salmonella* sp., and *E. coli*. *In vitro* antibacterial activity was performed by well diffusion method in nutrient agar. The extract showed significant effect on the tested organisms. The extract of *Calatropis procera* showed maximum zone of inhibition against *Xanthomonas* sp. whereas, lowest against *Salmonella* and fruit extract of *Tribulus terresteris* maximum zone of inhibition against *E. coli* and *Xanthomonas* whereas, lowest against *Salmonella* sp. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) was measured by modified agar well method. *C. procera* extracts were diluted to concentrations for ranging from 100 to 0.56 mg/mL and *T. terrestris* extracts were diluted to concentrations ranging from 100 to 0.78 mg/mL. The definitive aspire of the research workers was to develop economically and technically effective antibacterial extract, which will be Bio-ecologically and eco-friendly for management of bacterial infection.

Keywords: *C. procera*; *Xanthomonas*, *E. coli*, *Salmonella*; Antibacterial

Introduction

Plants are a rich source of different types of medicines. Approximately 20% of the plants found in the world have been submitted to pharmaceutical or biological tests and a sustainable number of new antibiotics on the market are obtained from natural or semi-synthetic resources. It has been reported that between the years 1983 and 1994 the systematic screening of antibacterial plant extracts represents a continuous effort to find new compounds with the potential to act against multi-resistant bacteria (Crag *et al.*, 1999). *Calotropis procera* L. belonging to the family Asclepiadaceae grows widely throughout the Indian subcontinent and used as a traditional medicinal plant with its unique properties (Oudhia, 1999). *Calotropis procera* is a better known as milkweed, habitat of Asian countries that includes, India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Thailand, Sri Lanka and China. Tribal people were using this plant parts to cure several illnesses such as toothache, earache, sprain, anxiety, pain, epilepsy, diarrhoea and mental disorders. Plants are reported to have anticancer, antimicrobial, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant properties (Gaurav Kumar *et al.*, 2010).

Tribulus terrestris L. (Zygophyllaceae) is an annual plant distributed in warm regions of Asia, Africa, Europe, America and Australia (Abeywickrama *et al.*, 1991; Kostova *et al.*, 2002). *T. terrestris* is used in folk medicine as tonic, aphrodisiac, analgesic, astringent, stomachic, antihypertensive, diuretic, lithon-triptic and urinary anti-infective (Ody, 2000).

Escherichia coli and *Salmonella* sp. is the major cause of many different infectious diseases in humans and animals and the most common bacteria isolated from animal infections (Arshad and Seed, 2015; Saltoglu *et al.*, 2015). *Xanthomonas*

axonopodis pv. *punicae* bacterium caused bacterial blight on pomegranate plant. Although the given study of antibacterial activities of *C. procera* (Stem) and *T. terrestris* (Fruit) extracts against bacteria were evaluated, the antibacterial activity of *C. procera* *T. terrestris* extract against clinical isolates of *E. coli* and *Salmonella* sp. and plant bacteria *X. axonopodis* pv. *punicae*

Material And Method

The experiment on antibacterial activities of *Calotropis procera* L. and *Tribulus terresteris* L. against three bacteria species was conducted at the plant pathological laboratory.

Extraction Of Plant Material

Dried plant material *Calotropis procera* (Stem) and *Tribulus terresteris* (Fruit) were extracted with 50% Ethanol solvent. The extraction was done for a period of 20-24 hrs continuously in Soxhlet apparatus. The unfiltered extracts were concentrated to dryness in hot air oven. These concentrated extracts were stored in glass bottles at 4°C temperature for future use. The sterilized discs of Whatmann filter paper no. 1 of 6 mm diameter were put into the extracts of each & every type viz., 50% ethanol extract-root, stem and leaf.

Bacteria Tested

All plant materials have tested against *Xanthomonas* Sp. (Plant Bacteria), *E. coli* and *Salmonella* Sp. (Human Bacteria) bacteria. The following strains used in present study were bought from NCMR Laboratory Pune.

Culture Media

The media used for antimicrobial test were Nutrient Agar, Nutrient Broth of hi media pvt.Ltd. Mumbai, India.

Inoculum Preparation

The test bacteria were inoculated into liquid medium i.e. Nutrient broth and suspensions were checked to provide approximately 10 CFU/ml.

Antibacterial Testing

The plant extract were tested for antibacterial activity in the agar well diffusion Assay using three bacterial strains. A diluted bacterial culture (0.5 ml) of respective strains poured over the base plants contain 10 ml of nutrient agar in sterile 9 cm petridishes and pour over nutrient agar. On cultured plate well formation by using cork-borer and each & every extracts were put on the center of petriplate contain solidified nutrient agar. Each plate was sealed with parafilm & incubated at 37⁰C temperature for 24 hrs, where after inhibition zone were recorded. Antibacterial activity was expressed as the ratios of the inhibition zone (mm) produced by extracts (Vander and Vlietnck, 1991).

Determination Of Minimum Inhibition Concentrations (Mic):

Table 1.: The Antibacterial activity of *C. procera* extracts

<i>C. procera</i> stem Extract against <i>Xanthomonas</i> Sp. (inhibition zone in mm)	A Well	B Well	C Well	Mean
	20.2	22.5	18.5	20.4±0.2

Following image shows antibacterial activity of *Calotropis procera* against *Xanthomonas* –

<i>C. procera</i> stem Extract against <i>E. Coli</i> (inhibition zone in mm)	C Well	E Well	F Well	Mean
	16	15.5	16.5	16±0.3

<i>C. procera</i> stem Extract against <i>Salmonella</i> Sp. (inhibition zone in mm)	C Well	E Well	F Well	Mean
	15	14.5	16	15.16±0.43

Following image shows antibacterial activity of *Calotropis procera* against *Salmonella sp.*-

The Antibacterial activity of *T. terrestris* extracts:

The antibacterial activities of the plant extracts were

evaluated by measuring the inhibition zone observed around the tested materials.

Table 1.: The Antibacterial activity of *T. terrestris* extracts

<i>T. terrestris</i> Fruit Extract against <i>Xanthomonas</i> Sp. (inhibition zone in mm)	D Well	E Well	F Well	Mean
	21.5	22	21	21.5±0.7

Following image shows antibacterial activity of *Tribulus terrestris* against *Xanthomonas sp.*

<i>T. terrestris</i> Fruit Extract against <i>E. Coli</i> (inhibition zone in mm)	A Well	B Well	C Well	D Well	Mean
	22.5	22	21.5	21	21.75±0.82

Following image shows antibacterial activity against *Salmonella sp.* –

<i>T. terrestris</i> Fruit Extract against <i>Salmonella Sp.</i> (inhibition zone in mm)	A Well	B Well	C Well	D Well	Mean
	20	21.5	20.5	21	20.75±0.45

According to study of Sharif *et al.* (2006) reported *Calotropis* extract were found inhibit growth of *E. coli* and *Salmonella sp.* Similar result were found the *T. terrestris* showed activity against *E. coli* and *Salmonella sp.* bacteria (Abbasoglu and Tosun, 1994).

The present investigation clearly reveals the antibacterial nature of this plant and suggests that this plant could be exploited in the management of diseases caused by these bacteria in human and plant systems and has same antibacterial activity as antibiotics shows. The phytochemical analysis

revealed that the active principle responsible for the activity is a phenolic compound. So the result established a good support for the use of *Calotropis procera* and *Tribulus terrestris* in traditional medicines. The results of our study have confirmed the uses of *C. procera* and *T. terrestris* should be formulated and more toxicological, pharmacological and clinical studies should be done for clarify the suitability of *T. terrestris* extract in control of *X. axonopodis* pv. *punicae*, *E. coli* and *Salmonella sp.* induced infections.

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